

S1: Recorded morphologies of screened isolates with potential ligninolytic ability.

Name	Description			Gram stain
	Shape	Colour	Texture	
E01	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Purple rods
E02	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Purple rods
E03	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Purple rods
E04	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Purple rods
E05	Irregular	Pink	Smooth	Pink rods
E06	Circular	Cream white	Smooth	Purple rods
E07	Circular	Cream white centre with clear outer part	Rough	Pink cocci
E08	Circular	Cream white centre with clear outer part	Rough	Pink rods
E09	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Pink cocci
E10	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Purple cocci
E11	Circular	Cream white	Smooth	Purple rods
E12	Circular	Cream white	Smooth	Pink rods
E13	Circular	Pink	Smooth	Purple rods
E14	Irregular	Cream white centre with clear outer part	Rough	Purple rods
E15	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Purple cocci
Z01	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Pink rods
Z02	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Pink rods
Z03	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Pink rods
Z04	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Pink rods
Z05	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Pink rods
Z06	Irregular	Cream white	Smooth	Pink rods

S2: Raw data of lignin assimilation of the 6 isolates showing potential robust ligninolytic activity.

Sample ID	Biomass	SD
Z06	6.40	0.100
Z04	2.06666667	0.208167
E02	0.56666667	0.23094
E09	1.70	0.300
Z05	4.20	0.300
E05	2.23333333	0.46188

S3: Univariate tests of significance for the biomass accumulated of the six isolates with potential ligninolytic activity.

Effect	Univariate Tests of Significance for Biomass accumulated Sigma-restricted parameterization Effective hypothesis decomposition				
	Intercept	157.8272	1	157.8272	1893.927
Sample ID	65.8628	5	13.1726	158.071	0.000000
Error	1.0000	12	0.0833		

S4: Post Hoc Tukey HSD statistical analysis of lignin assimilation of the six isolates.

Cell no.	Tukey HSD test; variable Biomass accumulated Approximate Probabilities for Post Hoc Tests Error: Between MS = .08333, df = 12.000						
	Sample ID	{1} .66667	{2} 6.500	{3} 2.1667	{4} 1.8000	{5} 4.3000	{6} 2.3333
1	E02		0.000159	0.000516	0.004504	0.000159	0.000278
2	Z06	0.000159		0.000159	0.000159	0.000161	0.000159
3	Z04	0.000516	0.000159		0.639010	0.000163	0.977469
4	E09	0.004504	0.000159	0.639010		0.000159	0.279685
5	Z05	0.000159	0.000161	0.000163	0.000159		0.000173
6	E05	0.000278	0.000159	0.977469	0.279685	0.000173	

S5: Raw data of growth rates of the three isolates with ligninolytic potential.

Sample ID	μ_{max}	SD
E02	0.447933	0.016605
Z06	0.355367	0.011102
Z04	0.3532	0.005302

S6: Univariate tests of significance for the growth rates of the three isolates with ligninolytic potential.

Effect	Univariate Tests of Significance for μ_{max} Sigma-restricted parameterization Effective hypothesis decomposition				
	SS	Degr. of Freedom	MS	F	p
Intercept	1.337492	1	1.337492	4689.189	0.000000
Sample ID	0.017548	2	0.008774	30.761	0.000702
Error	0.001711	6	0.000285		

S7: Post Hoc Tukey HSD statistical analysis of the growth rates of the three isolates.

Cell No.	Tukey HSD test; variable μ_{max} Approximate Probabilities for Post Hoc Tests Error: Between MS = .00029, df = 6.0000			
	Sample ID	{1} .44793	{2} .35320	{3} .35537
1	E02		0.001326	0.001479
2	Z04	0.001326		0.986601
3	Z06	0.001479	0.986601	

S8: Fermentation of the three strains isolated from herbivore dung. Right (A) shows the before and after fermentation while left (B) shows the minute gas bubbles formed by two strains (E02 and Z06) highlighted in the red box.

S9: Potential enzyme activity observed through decolourisation of phenol red, methylene blue and ABTS. Under aerobic conditions, phenol red turned fuchsia and no decolourisation was observed for methylene blue and ABTS while under anaerobic conditions, phenol red and methylene blue were decolourised by all strains while ABTS remained unchanged.

S10: Shows the forward and reverse sequences of the isolates studied.

> *Citrobacter amalonaticus* (E02) 16SF

CAGCCATGCCGCGTGTATGAAGAAGGCCTTCGGGTTGTAAAGTACTTTCAGCGGG
GAGGAAGGGGTTGAGGTTAATAACCTTAGCCATTGACGTTACCCGCAGAAGAAGC
ACCGGCTAACTCCGTGCCAGCAGCCGCGGTAATACGGAGGGTGAAGCGTTAATC
GGAATTACTGGGCGTAAAGCGCACGCAGGCGGTCTGTCAAGTCGGATGTGAAATC
CCCGGGCTCAACCTGGGAAGTGCATTCGAAACTGGCAGGCTTGAGTCTCGTAGAG
GGGGGTAGAATTCCAGGTGTAGCGGTGAAATGCGTAGAGATCTGGAGGAATACCG
GTGGCGAAGGCGGCCCCCTGGACGAAGACTGACGCTCAGGTGCGAAAGCGTGGG
GAGCAAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCACGCCGTAAACGATGTCTATTTGGA
GGTTGTGCCCTTGAGGCGTGGCTTCCGGAGCTAACGCGTTAAATAGACCGCCTGG
GGAGTACGGCCGCAAGGTTAAACTCAAATGAATTGACGGGGGCCCGCACAAAGC
GGTGGAGCATGTGGTTTAATTCGATGCAACGCGAAGAACCTTACCTGGTCTTGACA
TCCACAGAACTTGGCAGAGATGCCTTGGTGCCTTCGGGAAGTGTGAGACAGGTGC
TGCATGGCTGTTCGTCAGCTCGTGTGTGAAATGTTGGGTAAAGTCCCGCAACGAG
CGCAACCCTTATCCTTTGTTGCCAGCGGTCCGGCCGGGAAGTCAAAGGAGACTGC
CAGTGATAAACTGGAGGAAGGTGGGGATGACGTCAAGTCATCATGGGCCTTACGA
CCAGGGCTACACACGTGCTACATGGCATATACAAAGAGAAGCGACCTCGCGAGAG
CAAGCGGACCTCATAAAAGTATGTCGTAGTCCGGATTGGAGTCTGCAACTCGACT
CCATGAAGTCGGAATCGCTAGTAATCGTGGATCAGAATGCACGGTGAATACGTTCC
CGGGCCTTG

> *Citrobacter amalonaticus* (E02) 16SR

ATTCGGTGGCTTCTGATCCACGATTACTAGCGATTCCGACTTCATGGAGTCGAGT
TGCAGACTCCAATCCGGACTACGACATACTTTATGAGGTCCGCTTGCTCTCGCGAG
GTCGCTTCTCTTTGTATATGCCATTGTAGCACGTGTGTAGCCCTGGTCGTAAGGGCC
ATGATGACTTGACGTCATCCCCACCTTCCCTCCAGTTTATCACTGGCAGTCTCCTTTG
AGTTCCCGGCCGGACCGCTGGCAACAAAGGATAAGGGTTGCGCTCGTTGCGGGA
CTTAACCAACATTTCAACAACACGAGCTGACGACAGCCATGCAGCACCTGTCTCA
CAGTTCCCGAAGGCACCAAGGCATCTCTGCCAAGTTCTGTGGATGTCAAGACCAG
GTAAGGTTCTTCGCGTTGCATCGAATTAACCACATGCTCCACCGCTTGTGCGGGC
CCCCGTCAATTCATTTGAGTTTTAACCTTGCGGCCGTACTCCCCAGGCGGTCTATTT
AACGCGTTAGCTCCGGAAGCCACGCCTCAAGGGCACAACCTCCAAATAGACATCG
TTTACGGCGTGGACTACCAGGGTATCTAATCCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCAC
CTGAGCGTCAGTCTTCGTCCAGGGGGCCGCTTCGCCACCGGTATTCCTCCAGATC
TCTACGCATTTACCGCTACACCTGGAATTCTACCCCCCTTACGAGACTCAAGCC
TGCCAGTTTCGAATGCAGTTCACAGGTTGAGCCCGGGGATTTACATCCGACTTG
ACAGACCGCCTGCGTGCCTTTACGCCAGTAATTCGATTAACGCTTGCACCCTC
CGTATTACCGCGGCTGCTGGCACGGAGTTAGCCGGTGCTTCTTCTGCGGGTAACGT
CAATGGC

> *Enterobacter aff. cloacae* (Z04) 16SF

TGCAGCCATGCCGCGTGTATGAAGAAGGCCTTCGGGTTGTAAAGTACTTTCAGCG
GGGAGGAAGGTGTTGTGGTTAATAACCGCAGCAATTGACGTTACCCGCAGAAGAA
GCACCGGCTAACTCCGTGCCAGCAGCCGCGGTAATACGGAGGGTGAAGCGTTAA
TCGGAATTACTGGGCGTAAAGCGCACGCAGGCGGTCTGTCAAGTCGGATGTGAAA

TCCCCGGGCTCAACCTGGGAACTGCATTTCGAAACTGGCAGGCTGGAGTCTTGTAG
AGGGGGGTAGAATTCAGGTGTAGCGGTGAAATGCGTAGAGATCTGGAGGAATAC
CGGTGGCGAAGGCGGCCCTGGACAAAGACTGACGCTCAGGTGCGAAAGCGTG
GGGAGCAAACAGGATTAGATAACCCTGGTAGTCCACGCCGTAAACGATGTTCGATTT
GGAGGTTGTGCCCTTGAGGCGTGGCTTCCGGAGCTAACGCGTTAAATCGACCGCC
TGGGGAGTACGGCCGCAAGGTTAAAACCTCAAATGAATTGACGGGGGCCCGCACA
AGCGGTGGAGCATGTGGTTTAATTCGATGCAACGCGAAGAACCTTACCTGGTCTT
GACATCCACAGAACTTTCCAGAGATGGATTGGTGCCTTCGGGAACTGTGAGACAG
GTGCTGCATGGCTGTCGTCAGCTCGTGTTGTGAAATGTTGGGTTAAGTCCCAGAAC
GAGCGCAACCCTTATCCTTTGTTGCCAGCGGTTAGGCCGGGAACTCAAAGGAGAC
TGCCAGTGATAAACTGGAGGAAGGTGGGGATGACGTCAAGTCATCATGGCCCTTA
CGACCAGGCTACACACGTGCTACAATGGCGCATACAAGAGAAGCGACCTCGCGA
GAGCAAGCGGACCTCATAAAGTGCCTCGTAGTCCGGATTGGAGTCTGCAACTCGA
CTCATGAAGTCGGAATCGCTAGTAATCGTAGATCAGAATGCTACGGTGAATACGTT
CCGGTCTTGTAC

> *Enterobacter aff. cloacae* (Z04) 16R

ACGATTACTAGCGGTTCCGACTTCATGGAGTCGAGTTGCAGACTCCAATCCGGACT
ACGACGCACTTTATGAGGTCCGCTTGCTCTCGCGAGGTCGCTTCTCTTTGTATGCG
CCATTGTAGCACGTGTGTAGCCCTGGTCGTAAGGGCCATGATGACTTGACGTCATC
CCCACCTTCCCTCCAGTTTATCACTGGCAGTCTCCTTTGAGTTCCCGGCCTAACCGC
TGGCAACAAAGGATAAGGGTTGCGCTCGTTGCGGGACTTAACCCAACATTTACACA
ACACGAGCTGACGACAGCCATGCAGCACCTGTCTCACAGTTCCCGAAGGCACCA
ATCCATCTCTGGAAAGTTCTGTGGATGTCAAGACCAGGTAAGGTTCTTCGCGTTGC
ATCGAATTAACCACATGCTCCACCGCTTGTGCGGGCCCCCGTCAATTCATTTGAG
TTTTAACCTTGCGGCCGTACTCCCCAGGCGGTTCGATTTAACGCGTTAGCTCCGGAA
GCCACGCCTCAAGGGCACAACCTCCAAATCGACATCGTTTACGGCGTGGACTACC
AGGGTATCTAATCCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCACCTGAGCGTCAGTCTTTGT
CCAGGGGGCCGCTTCGCCACCGGTATTCTCCAGATCTCTACGCATTTACCCGCT
ACACCTGGAATTCTACCCCCCTCTACAAGACTCCAGCCTGCCAGTTTCGAATGCAG
TTCCCAGGTTGAGCCCGGGGATTTACATCCGACTTGACAGACCGCCTGCGTGCG
CTTTACGCCAGTAATTCGATTAACGCTTGCACCCTCCGTATTACCGCGGCTGCTG
GCACGGAGTTAGCCGGTGCTTCTTCTGCGGGTAACGTCAATTGCTGTGGTATAACC
ACACACCTTCCCTCCCGCTGAAGTACTTACACCCGAGGCTCTCATAACGCGCATG
GCTGCATCAGCTTGCGCCATTGTGCAATATTCCCTACC

> *Acinetobacter aff. proteolyticus* (Z06) 16SF

ACCTGATCAGCCATGCCGCGTGTGTGAAGAAGGCCTTTTGGTTGTAAAGCACTTT
AAGCGAGGAGGAGGCTACTAAGATTAATACTCTTGGATAGTGGACGTTACTCGCA
GAATAAGCACCGGCTAACTCTGTGCCAGCAGCCGCGGTAATACAGAGGGTGCAG
CGTTAATCGGATTTACTGGGCGTAAAGCGTGCCTAGGCGGCTTTTTAAGTTCGGATG
TGAAATCCCCGAGCTTAACTTGGGAATTGCATTCGATACTGGGAAGCTAGAGTATG
GGAGAGGATGGTAGAATTCCAGGTGTAGCGGTGAAATGCGTAGAGATCTGGAGGA
ATACCGATGGCGAAGGCAGCCATCTGGCCTAATACTGACGCTGAGGTACGAAAGC
ATGGGGAGCAAACAGGATTAGATAACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTAAACGATGTCTAC
TAGCCGTTGGGGCCTTTGAGGCTTTAGTGGCGCAGCTAACGCGATAAGTAGACCG
CCTGGGGAGTACGGTTCGCAAGACTAAAACCTCAAATGAATTGACGGGGGCCCGCA
CAAGCGGTGGAGCATGTGGTTTAATTCGATGCAACGCGAAGAACCTTACCTGGTC

TTGACATAGTAAGAACTTTCCAGAGATGGATTGGTGCCTTCGGGAACTTACATACA
GGTGCTGCATGGCTGTCGTCAGCTCGTGTCTGAGATGTTGGGTTAAGTCCCGCA
ACGAGCGCAACCCTTTTCCTTATTTGCCAGCGGGTTAAGCCGGGAACTTTAAGGAT
ACTGCCAGTGACAAACTGGAGGAAGGCGGGGACGACGTCAAGTCATCATGGGCC
CTTACGACCAGGGCTACACACGTGCTACAATGGTCGGTACAAAGGGTTGCTACCT
AGCGATAGGATGCTAATCTCAAAGCGATCGTAGTCCGGATTGGAGTCTGCACTCG
ACTCATGAAGTCGGAATCGCTAGTAATCGCGGATCAGATGCGCGTGAATACGTTTC
CTGGCCTTGT

> *Acinetobacter* aff. *proteolyticus* (Z06) 16SF 16SR

CCGGCGGCATTCTGATCCGCGATTACTAGCGATTCCGACTTCATGGAGACGAGTTG
CAGACTCCAATCCGGACTACGATCGGTTTTTTGAGATTAGCGTCCGATCGCTAGGT
AGCAACCCTTTGTACCGACCATTGTAGCACGTGTGTAGCCCTGGCCGTAAGGGTCA
TGATGACTTGACGTCGTCCCCGCCTTCCCTCCAGTTTGTCACTGGAAGAATCCTTAA
AGGGCCCGGATTAACCCGCTGGAAAATAAGGAAAAGGGTTGCGCTCGTTGCGGG
ACTTAACCCAACATCTCACGACACGAGCTGACGACAGCCATGCAGCACCTGTATG
TAAGTTCCCGAAGGCACCAATCCATCTCTGGAAAGTTCTTACTATGTCAAGACCAG
GTAAGGATCTTCGCGTTGAATGGAATTAACCACATGCTCCACCGCTTGTGCTGGC
CCCCGCCAATCATTTGAGTTTTAGTCTTTCGACCGTACTCCCCAGGCGGTCTACT
TATCGCGTTAGCTGCGCCACTAAAGCCTCAAAGGCCCAACGGCTAGTAGACATC
GTTTACGGCATGGACTACCAGGGTATCTAATCCTGTTTGTCTCCCATGCTTTCGTAC
CTCAGCGTCAGTATTAGGCCAGATGGCTGCCTTCGCCATCGGTATTCCCTCCAGATCT
CTACGCATTTACCGCTACACCTGGAATTCTACCATCCTCTCCCATACTCTAGCTTC
CCAGTATCGAATGCAATTCCCAAGTTAAGCTCGGGGATTTACATCCGACTTAAA
GCCGCCTACGCACGCTTTACGCCAGTAAATCCGATTAACGCTCGCACCCCTCTGTA
TTACCGCGGCTGCTGGCACAGAGTAGCCGGTGCTTATTCTGCGAGTAACGTCCACT
ATCCAGAG

S11: In a table, the raw data from Py-GCMS analysis of the three strains.

Sample code (E02)		
Ret Time	Area %	Compound name
2,267	0,2	Thiirane
2,409	0,37	Acetic acid ethyl ester
3,039	0,55	Methyl isobutyrate
3,16	3,86	2-Propenoic acid, ethyl ester
3,345	48,12	2H-Pyran-2-one, 6-heptyltetrahydro-
4,213	0,57	Toluene
4,604	0,2	2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-
5,591	1,25	Cyclohexene, 4-ethenyl-
7,068	38,78	1,3,7-Octatrien-5-yne
8,616	0,24	Benzene, 2-propenyl-
9,692	0,46	Benzene, (1-methylethenyl)-
29,556	0,21	Benzene, 3-butenyl-
31,265	0,23	(.+/-)-3-(2-Carboxy-trans-propenyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-trans-1-carboxylic acid,[1.alpha., 3.beta.(E)]-
32,002	0,23	2,4-Pentadienoic acid, 5-(8-hydroxy-1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-6-oxabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-8-yl)-3-methyl-, methyl ester, [1R-[1.alpha.,5.alpha.]-
34,952	0,68	1-Cyclopentyl-2-phenyl-1-propene
35,913	2,34	1,6-Heptadiene, 2-methyl-6-phenyl-
37,945	0,81	1,6-Heptadiene, 2-methyl-6-phenyl-
41,398	0,52	Benzene, 1,1'-(2-pentene-1,5-diyl)bis-
42,925	0,39	Benzene, 1,1'-(2-pentene-1,5-diyl)bis-
Sample code (Z04)		
Ret Time	Area %	Compound name
2,419	8,19	Acetic acid ethyl ester
3,166	2,24	2-Propenoic acid, ethyl ester
3,337	53,08	Methyl methacrylate
4,611	0,73	1-Octene
5,301	3,38	Cyclotrisiloxane, hexamethyl-
7,056	31,77	Benzene, (2-nitroethyl)-
10,207	0,62	trisiloxane, 1,1,1,5,5,5-hexamethyl-3-[(trimethylsilyl)oxy]-

Sample code (Z06)		
End time	Area %	Compound name
2,414	7,05	Acetic acid ethyl ester
3,333	41,91	Methyl methacrylate
4,204	2,82	Toluene
4,607	2,21	1-Octene
5,276	1,2	Cyclotrisiloxane, hexamethyl-
5,774	2,57	2,4-Dimethylhept-1-ene
7,045	23,29	1,3,5,7-Cyclooctatetraene
10,201	0,57	Cyclotetrasiloxane, octamethyl-
12,991	6,04	Phenol, 2-methoxy-
14,068	1,63	1-Octanethiol
15,685	0,83	Phenol, 2-methoxy-3-methyl-
16,095	4,05	Creosol
18,565	1,48	Phenol, 4-ethyl-2-methoxy-
19,562	2,76	2-Methoxy-4-vinylphenol
20,753	0,89	Phenol, 2-methoxy-3-(2-propenyl)-
23,065	0,72	Octane, 2-bromo-

S12: Image of the gel electrophoresis depicting all isolates studied. The three isolates selected for this study have been highlighted in the red box.

